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Flavone glycosides from the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia*

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FROM the hot ethanolic extract of the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia* two flavone glycosides, (i) acacetin-7-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside and (ii) 5,7-dimethyl apigenin-4'-*O*- β -D(+) galactopyranoside and also an anthraquinone glycoside have been isolated and studied.

The first compound, m.p. 244°-45°, molecular formula $C_{22}H_{12}O_{10}$, when hydrolysed with mineral acid gave acacetin $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ and glucose. The structure of acacetin has been confirmed by analysis colour reactions spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The position of the sugar linkage has been shown to be with 7-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shift using aluminium chloride¹ and sodium acetate². That glucose is present in the pyranose form has been proved by periodate oxidation and nature of the glycoside linkage as β - has been confirmed by its hydrolysis with emulsin.

The other flavone glycoside m.p. 178°-80° (d), molecular formula $C_{23}H_{24}O_{10}$, on hydrolysis with mineral acid gave an aglycone $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ (m.p. 295°) and galactose. The aglycone has been shown to be 5,7-dimethyl apigenin by analysis, colour reactions spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The position of the sugar linkage has been shown to be with the 4'-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shifts using ethoxide reagent³. That galactose is in the pyranose form has been established by periodate oxidation and the β -linkage of the glycoside by hydrolysis with emulsin.

The compound acacetin-7-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside is known and has been reported earlier from several plant sources^{4,5}. The other glycoside, 5,7-dimethyl apigenin-4'-*O*- β -D(+) galactopyranoside, has not been reported earlier from any plant source, though another glycoside namely 5,7-dimethyl-4'-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside has been recently reported by Dubey and Mishra⁶ from sugar cane peelings.

The third compound isolated from this plant is an anthraquinone glycoside which is being studied and will be reported later.

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Mixed ligand complexes of Bis (ethylacetoacetato) Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with nitrogen donors

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β DIKETONES and related compounds which exhibit keto-enol tautomerism react with metal cations to form complexes which behave as Lewis acids and form adducts with Lewis bases. Several such base adducts of β -diketonates of Zn(II) and copper(II) have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵. The complexes of β -keto esters closely resemble those of β -diketonates. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the base adduct formation with ethylacetoacetato complexes and this communication describes eight base adducts of bis(ethylacetoacetato) Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with quinoline and isoquinoline.

Experimental

Metal chelates were prepared by reacting ethanolic solution of metal chlorides with ethylacetoacetato in (1 : 2) ratio followed by dropwise addition of sodium acetate solution. The precipitated compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. Bis(ethylacetoacetato) metal(II) was suspended in minimum volume of ethanol and base was added in (1 : 2) ratio and the mixture refluxed till a clear solution was obtained. On keeping the clear solution overnight crystalline compounds separated out.

Metal and nitrogen in the compounds were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in *M*/1000 acetone solution using "Toshniwal's Conductivity Bridge". Infra-red spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer and electronic spectra in *M*/100 (chloroform base mixture) solution with Hilger Watt Uvispek spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility